

Gamcha of Bankura – A Traditional Craft in Handlooms

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Abstract

The craft of making gamcha in handloom has been practised by the 'Tanti' community in Bankura, West Bengal, and has seen a decline in demand due to increased raw material costs, poor wages, use of synthetic yarn, and lower market prices. The lack of education among artisans, the use of banned dyes and chemicals, and limited product variety have also contributed to the decline. However, the industry has strengths such as excellent weave quality, inherited craftsmanship, and lower capital requirements. A SWOT analysis reveals advantages and disadvantages, offering opportunities for designers to improve the industry while preserving the essence of gamcha in diversified products.

Keywords: Bankura, Craft, Gamcha, Handloom, Weaving, West Bengal

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1. Introduction

The handloom sector can create employment generation opportunities amongst rural people and contribute nearly 15% of the total cloth production. According to the Ministry of Textiles, Government of India, Annual Report 2018–2019, 95% of the world's handwoven fabric comes from India. According to the 4th All India Handloom Census, 28.2 lakh handlooms operate across India. The average number of weavers per household in rural and urban areas is 1.04 and 1.10, respectively [1]. West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Assam and Tripura account for over 78.6% of the country's handloom saree production.

Most of the problems the handloom industry faces are perpetual and this sector has been seriously threatened by a sharp rise in yarn, dye, and chemical costs [2]. The share of income through handloom weaving in West Bengal has decreased, indicating considerable occupational diversification among the artisans engaged in handloom weaving. Numerous studies on the diverse facets of the handloom industry have been compiled by academics, Central and State Government agencies, and Research organisations [3-6].

The craft of making *gamcha* has been practised for a very long period in the Bankura district of West Bengal. The 'Tanti' communities of *Kenjakura*, a village located in the Bankura-I block and Rajogram, near the main town of Bankura, are mainly engaged in this craft for a long time. In earlier days, the majority of villagers were involved in this textile craft. But now, the whole scenario has changed, and most artisans are ready to choose another source of income to sustain their livelihood. The artisans of Rajogram village quickly change their profession of *gamcha* making to other professions. However, because of distance and communication, the artisans of *Kenjakura* village continue this craft and prefer to weave the traditional *gamcha* to maintain their way of life.

The gender-wise role of making *gamcha* in the *Kenjakura* village is based on the workload of that specific job to produce a *gamcha*. Generally, the male members of the village are doing heavier works, such as 'Punni kara' (Creeling), 'Charka gutano' (Ball warping), 'Dhal gutano' (Beaming) and 'Tant bandha/ Tant bona' (Weaving) and sometimes, they have also engaged in allied activities viz., 'Suto bulano' (Yarn winding), 'Khi porano' (Drafting), 'Sana gatha' (Denting) and 'Noli pakano' (Pirn winding). Previously, the dyeing was also performed by the male members of the family. The female members of the family are doing lighter works such as 'Suto bulano' (Yarn winding), 'Khi porano' (Drafting), 'Sana gatha' (Denting) and 'Noli pakano' (Pirn winding). Sometimes, they are involved in 'Tant bandha/ Tant bona' (Weaving) operations to help their male counterparts. The working hours for making *gamcha* vary based on gender and roles in the family. Male family members work from 5 a.m. to 10 a.m., then engage in other work. They rest for half an hour before completing the warping,

drafting, and denting processes. Female family members work during their leisure time. In the morning, they are engaged in their household activities, such as cleaning the house, making food for family members, etc. Then in the afternoon, after getting a short rest, like male members, they are engaged in weaving and other work such as pirn winding up to the evening. However, when the workload increased, they used to weave and do the pirn winding in the evenings until 8 p.m.

2. Handwoven Gamcha

Since the beginning, the *gamcha* of Bankura has been used in various cultural, social, and economic functions. The primary function of this *gamcha* is as a bath towel. In addition, these are used for a variety of other purposes, including birth rituals, marriage rituals, death rituals, puja, etc. Occasionally, farmers and daily workers use this *gamcha* as headgear for carrying food items. In the past, this *gamcha* was also worn as a *lungi* and given as a gift. This is also used to make Punjabi, sari and blouses, along with other garments.

3. Raw Materials

3.1 Yarn

Cotton of various counts ranging from 2/40 Ne, 17 Ne, 2/17 Ne, 40 Ne, 60 Ne, and 2/60 Ne is used for making the *gamcha*. 2/40 Ne is generally used as the warp yarn. The yarns are sold to the market in the 'Bundle' form. The cost of yarns varies depending on the colour and fineness. Table 1 shows the cost of dyed yarn according to count.

Table 1 - The Cost of Different Counts of Dyed Yarn

Colours	Cost/Bundle (Rs.)		
	17 Ne, 2/17 Ne	2/40 Ne	40 Ne, 60 Ne, 2/60 Ne
Red	160	168	180
Purple	145	158	167
Green	220	240	280
Blue	285	315	400
Golden yellow	140	140	140
Mustard yellow	140	140	140
Pink	140	140	140
Parrot green	247	260	275
White (Bluing agent)	90	90	90

3.2 Dye

In earlier days, cotton yarns were purchased from Barabazar, Kolkata. Then those yarns were processed for dyeing by the *Tanti* family members in their village. But, presently, the yarns are purchased from the Barabazar by some agents of Bankura's main town. Then those yarns are processed in Rajogram village and other parts of Bankura, for dyeing purposes. After that, those yarns are sent back to the same agents. Those dyed cotton yarns are purchased by the *Tanti* from those agents. There are several colours, viz., red, purple, blue, green, golden yellow, mustard yellow, pink, parrot green, and white, are being used for making the *gamcha*. The red, purple, and pink colours are produced from naphthol, whereas the blue, green, golden yellow, mustard yellow and parrot green colours are obtained from vat dye. The white colour is bleached yarns treated with a bluing agent. The artisans called this naphthol colour '*Kachha Rong*' and the vat colour '*Pakka Rong*'. Among these colours, red, purple, blue, and green are the most commonly used.

3.3 Tools and Equipment

Figure 1 depicts various tools and equipment used for producing hand-woven *gamcha*.

Figure 1: Various tools and equipment used

4. Flow Chart of the Processes

Figure 2 shows the different stages of making hand-woven *gamcha* through a flow chart.

Figure 2: The different stages of the production process of hand-woven gamcha

5. Production Process

5.1 Warping

The first process of warping starts with the conversion of dyed cotton hanks purchased from the local markets to small leases with the help of *boro charki* and a hand-driven winding device (*Latay*). This process is known as 'yarn winding' (*Suto Bulano*). The female allied members of the family mostly performed this process. Then those small leases are placed on many small *charkis* on a rectangular wooden frame called a creel (*Archi*). Those small *charkis*

are called bobbin (*Archi charki*), and the process is known as 'creeling' (*Punni kara*). The male allied members of the family perform this job.

Parallely, a primary warping process is performed by winding the warp yarns from those bobbins onto a rectangular wooden frame called the peg warping device (*Punni ara*). This process passes those warp yarns through a reed (*Punni hata*) made of bamboo cane. This process is known as 'denting for peg warping' (*Sana gatha*). This process helps to decide the width and the length of the final fabric, and it also helps to count the number and colour-wise grouping of the yarns. The male allied members of the family perform this process. The weaver also decides the dimensions of the warp at this stage. Some weavers use a big rotating drum, apart from the peg warping device, for this process. But this drum is placed at a far distance from the weaver's village. So, most people didn't prefer this drum.

Then from that peg warping device, the yarns are collected and rolled to make a ball-like structure called a ball warp (*Punni*) with the help of a conical roller called a 'hand-driven winding device' (*Latay*). Presently, it has been modified to a cylindrical roller called '*Lately*'. This process is known as 'Ball warping' (*Charka gutano*). The male allied members of the family perform this process.

After that, from that ball warp, a rectangular tunnel is formed with the help of a wooden rod called the lease rod (*Dangi*). Then those tunnel-formed yarns are passed through a reed made of bamboo cane. This process is known as 'Primary denting' (*Sana gatha*). The male allied members of the family perform this process. Then those denting warping yarns are rolled on a wooden roller called a 'Weaver's beam' (*Dhal*). This process is known as 'Beaming' (*Dhal gutano*). The male allied members of the family perform this process. Sometimes, this process is done as a commission job by some master craftsperson. Then the weavers' beam is placed on a frame loom for the upcoming processes. Then the warping process is finished, and the weaver's beam is ready for weaving. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the creeling process and beaming process for warping respectively.

Figure 3: Creeling process

Figure 4: Beaming process for warping

5.2 Drafting and Denting

Then from that weaver's beam, the warp yarns are first passed through the heald eyes (*Bow*) of the heald shaft (*frame*) with the help of a metallic hook and form a rectangular tunnel. This process is known as 'Drafting' (*Khi porano*) shown in Figure 5. In this process, one warp yarn passes per one heald eye. This process is performed by both male and female members of the family. After that, a simultaneous process is performed, i.e., the yarns coming from those heald eyes pass through the dents of a reed (*Sana*). This process is known as 'Final denting' (*Sana gatha*) depicted in Figure 6. In this process, two yarns pass per one dent in the selvedge section, and one thread in the body section is passed per one. Male and female allied family members also do this process. These two processes require two people at the same time. These two processes are sometimes performed as commission work by master craftspeople. Now the total frame loom is ready for the upcoming processes.

Figure 5: Drafting process

Figure 6: Denting procedure

5.3 Weaving

Then those rectangular tunnels formed by yarns from that reed are attached to a wooden stick called a beam stick (*Fupi kathi*) which is attached to the cloth roll (*Kolloraj*) of the frame loom. Then the frame loom is ready for the 'Weaving process' (*Tant bandha*) shown in Figure 7. The male or female allied members of the family perform this process. In this process, the enrolled pirns (*Noli*) are passed in between the rectangular tunnel of the warping yarns with the help of a shuttle (*Maku*). This movement of the shuttle is performed using a wooden handle called the Picking grip (*Muthokath / Hatol*). Then the newly inserted yarn is transferred to the fell of cloth with the help of a sley (*Kol*). Then the heald shaft is changed with the help of a paddle (*Jhap*) attached to each heald shaft. Then again, the weft yarn is passed in between the rectangular tunnels. Then again, the same procedure is being performed. In this way, weaving of the *Gamcha* is done on a frame loom.

Figure 7: Weaving process

5.4 Pirn Winding

In this process, a set of yarns is required to pass between the warping tunnels for weaving purposes. This set of yarn is known as 'weft yarn'. For this purpose, the weft yarns are placed on the pirns (*Noli Khari*) with the help of a *charki* (*Boro charki*) and a hand-operated *charka* (*Hat charka*). This process is known as 'Pirn winding' (*Noli pakano*) as shown in Figure 8. The male or female allied members of a tanti family perform this process. This process is performed simultaneously with the weaving.

Figure 8: Pirn winding

6. Weaves and their Significance

Bankura *gamcha* is a yarn-dyed handwoven fabric. All the motifs and patterns are applied to the fabric with the help of weaving. Traditionally, the weavers use Huck-a-back weave, which has the special characteristic of gaining moisture very quickly. Some other weaves used to make this handwoven *gamcha* are plain weave, honey-comb weave, mixing plain and huck-a-back weave etc. Traditionally, the weavers use these weaves in a certain way such that the weave itself plays the role of a motif, and by repeating those weaves, it plays the role of a pattern. Sometimes, by manipulating the reed no. or, by changing the size of the weave repeat, the weavers try to ornament the *gamcha's* aesthetical appearance with a specific name of that modified *gamcha*.

7. Motifs, patterns and their significance

Several motifs and patterns are used in the Bankura *gamcha*, inspired mainly by the daily used items and the Kenjakura villagers' daily words. Some of the motifs with their patterns are discussed below and shown in Figure 9.

7.1 Dhansis

This motif is inspired by the 'paddy crop'. Paddy is the most grown crop in that village and in Bengali, it is called 'Dhansis'. Traditionally, this motif and its name came verbally from the ancestors of the *Tantipara* weavers. This motif is generally used in the weft direction of the 'Plain check *gamcha*' and on the 'Tom-tom plain check *gamcha*' on a single side. This pattern is created by twisting two different coloured yarns by hand and inserting those twisted yarns in a single direction of the *gamcha* at the time of picking. This pattern is generally created to differentiate the handloom *gamcha* from the power loom *gamcha*.

7.2 Gol Dor

This motif is inspired by the 'round metallic chain'. Traditionally, this motif and its name also came verbally from the ancestors of the *Tantipara* weavers. This pattern is generally used in the weft direction of the 'Towala *gamcha*' and on the 'Chera-phara *gamcha*' on both sides in combination with the Chain pattern and the Cycle chain pattern. This pattern is created by a plain weave.

7.3 Chain

This motif is inspired by the 'metallic chain'. Traditionally, this motif and its name also came verbally from the forefathers of the *Tantipara* weavers. This pattern is also used on the weft direction of the 'Towala *gamcha*' and the 'Chera-phara *gamcha*' on both sides in combination with the *Gol dor* pattern and the Cycle chain pattern. This pattern is created by a plain weave.

7.4 Cycle Chain

This motif is inspired by the ‘chain of a cycle’. This pattern is also used on the weft direction of the *Towala gamcha* and the *Chera-phara gamcha* on both sides in combination with the *Gol dor* pattern and the Chain pattern. This pattern is also produced by a plain weave.

7.5 Baki

This motif is inspired by the ‘nature of line orientation as well as from the waves of water’. This pattern is used on both sides in the weft direction of the ‘*Mukum gamcha*’ and on the ‘*Harkum gamcha*’. This pattern is created by twill weave.

Figure 9: Different famous motifs on different gamcha

8. Reeds and their Significance

There are several types of reeds which are used to make the *gamcha* of Kenjakura, such as 600 dents per 36 inches (Reed count – 33^s stock port), 625 dents per 36 inches (Reed count – 35^s stock port), 650 dents per 36 inches (Reed count – 36^s stock port), 675 dents per 36 inches (Reed count – 38^s stock port), 700 dents per 36 inches (Reed count – 39^s stock port).

The most commonly used reed count is 36^s stock ports, i.e., 650 dents per 36 inches. Reed counts vary based on the specific requirements of the buyer.

9. Colours and their Combinations

The colours used for making the *gamcha* are red, purple, blue, green, golden yellow, mustard yellow, pink, parrot green, and white. Generally, the combinations are made from red, purple, blue, green, golden yellow, and white colours. Nowadays, some extra colours are added to enhance the aesthetic value of the *gamcha*.

10. Yarns and their Combinations

Cotton is the most commonly used yarn for making the *gamcha*. Several yarn combinations are being developed for the production of *gamcha* and other diverse products. Table 2 shows some of these products and yarn combinations.

Table 2 - Yarn Combinations for Different Products

Warp (Ne)	Weft (Ne)	Type of product
2/40	17	<i>Gamcha</i>
2/60	60	Saree and Stoles
2/17	17	Curtain, Hand towel, Table runner, Cushion cover
17	17	Santhal saree (Here, the warp yarns are used by sizing with the rice extracted from the water, or Sabu dana)
2/40	40	Stole

11. The Layout of the Gamcha

The layout of Kenjakura's handmade *gamcha* varies from one *gamcha*'s type to another *gamcha*'s type, and the size of the *gamcha* varies from customer to customer. Apart from these, the other design elements are the same for a single type of *gamcha*. The most commonly used sizes of the *gamcha* fabric are 70/32 inches and 86/32 inches. Apart from these two popular sizes, several other options are also available, i.e., 70/30 inches, 70/31 inches, 80/30 inches, 80/31 inches, 80/32 inches, 86/30 inches, 86/31 inches etc. Traditionally, the craftsmen call this 70-inch *gamcha* 'Char hat *gamcha*' and the 86-inch *gamcha* 'panch hat *gamcha*'. For 'Baby towel *gamcha*', the options are 52/30 inches, 52/31 inches, 52/32 inches, 61/30 inches, 61/31 inches, and 61/32 inches. For puja purposes, the most commonly used sizes of the *gamcha* are 44/30 inches, 44/31 inches, and 44/32 inches.

12. Types of Kenjakura's Handmade *Gamcha*

There are several types of *gamcha* which are available in the Kenjakura village. The weavers of Kenjakura village can make about 10 types of *gamcha*, such as 'Plain check *gamcha*', 'Tom-tom plain check *gamcha*', 'Towala *gamcha*', 'Chera-phara *gamcha*', 'Mukum *gamcha*', 'Harkum *gamcha*', 'Choto phul *gamcha*', 'Boro phul *gamcha*', 'Bibi dial *gamcha*' and 'Honeycomb *gamcha*'. From these *gamchas*, the most popular and well-known *gamcha* are 'Plain check *gamcha*' and 'Towala *gamcha*'.

Figure 10: Different types of famous handloom *gamchas* of Kenjakura village

12.1 Plain Check *Gamcha*

Figure 11: Plain check *gamcha*

Plain check *gamcha* (Figure 11) is the second most sold-out *gamcha* after *Towala gamcha* in the Kenjakura village. It is also a very well-known *gamcha* in the whole of West Bengal. It is famous for its design elements like colour, texture, pattern, and weave. It is generally available in 4 colour combinations, i.e., 'red with white', 'purple with white', 'green with white', 'blue with white' and sometimes it is available in a 'golden yellow with white' colour combinations.

Plain check gamcha is generally made up of 2/40 Ne yarn in the warp direction in combination with the 17 Ne yarn in the weft direction. The drafting and denting plan for the selvedge section is maintained by using 1 end per 1 heald eye of the heald shaft and 2 ends per 1 dent of the reed. For the body part, the drafting plan is the same as the selvedge section, but for the denting purpose, 1 end is passed per 1 dent of the reed. Generally, 2 heald shafts are used for making this *Plain check gamcha*, and the reed count varies from 38^s stock ports to 40^s stock ports depending on the width of the *gamcha*.

The whole part of the *Plain check gamcha* will consist of mainly two parts, i.e., the selvedge and the body part. Again, the selvedge part of the plain check *gamcha* will consist of several factors with their specific names and denting orders, i.e., 'Agari consists of 10 dents', followed by 'Koni consists of 6 dents', 'Parh consists of 20/22/25 dents (based on the width of the *gamcha*)', 'Gondi consists of 24 dents', 'Churi consists of 6 dents' and 'Matha pati consists of 15 dents'. The body part will consist of two parts, i.e., 'Toila pati consists of 15 dents', followed

by the 'Check consists of 2 dents and this pattern of *Toila pati* and Check will continue for the whole body. Then again, this pattern will end up with the selvedge portion starting with *Matha pati* after completing 62 numbers of *Toila pati* (which also depends on the width of the *gamcha*). So, the total number of *Toila pati* and *Matha pati* on a single Plain check *gamcha* will be $62+2=64$.

Theoretically, *Matha pati* and *Toila pati* will form a square on the *gamcha*, which means if *Matha pati* and *Toila pati*, 15 dents are present, it means the total number of yarns present in *Matha pati* and *Toila pati* is also 15 yarns; so, at the time of weft insertion, the total number of yarns should be 15 yarns. But practically it doesn't happen. The weavers usually insert the picks according to their eye resemblance.

On a single side of the *Plain check gamcha*, one pattern is created by twisting two different coloured yarns crossly by hand and inserting those twisted yarns in a single direction of the *gamcha* at the time of picking. This pattern is generally created to differentiate the handloom *gamcha* from the power loom *gamcha*. The motif of this pattern is called '*Dhansis*'. This motif is inspired by the 'Paddy crop'. As paddy is the most grown crop in the Kenjakura village and Bengali it is termed as '*Dhansis*'. Traditionally this motif and its name came verbally from the forefathers of the *Tantipara* weavers. The layout of the plain check *gamcha* is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Layout of plain check gamcha

Technical sheet

- Weaving plan drawing
- Loom used – Frame loom
- Name of the weave – Plain weave
- No. of heald shafts – 02
- Reed count – 38^s stock port to 40^s stock ports (depending on the width of the *gamcha*)
- Count of warp – 2/40 Ne
- Count of weft – 17 Ne
- Drafting plan - 1 end per 1 heald eye (in both the selvedge portion and the body part)
- Denting plan - 2 ends per 1 dent (in the selvedge portion), 1 end per 1 dent (in the body part)
- EPI – 40
- PPI – 44

12.2 Towala Gamcha

Figure 13: Towala gamcha

Towala gamcha as shown in Figure 13, is the most popular *gamcha* in the whole Kenjakura village. It is the most famous and well-known *gamcha* not only in the Kenjakura village or, in the Bankura district, but it is famous throughout the West Bengal, and it is called ‘Bankura *gamcha*.’ It is well-known for its design elements such as colour, texture, pattern, weaves, and its most important parameter, i.e., it has a very high moisture regain property. It is generally available in 4 colour combinations, i.e., red with white, purple with white, green with white and blue with white and sometimes it is available in a golden yellow with the white colour combination. Its good moisture regains property; texture and pattern are enhanced by its famous weave, i.e., Huck-a-back weave in combination with a plain weave.

Towala gamcha is generally made by using 2/40 Ne yarn in the warp direction in combination with the 17 Ne yarn in the weft direction. The drafting and denting plan for the selvedge section is maintained by using 1 end per 1 heald eye of the heald shaft and 2 ends per 1 dent of the reed. For the body part, the drafting plan will be the same as the selvedge section but for the denting purpose, 1 end is passed per 1 dent of the reed. Generally, 4 heald shafts are used for making this *Towala gamcha*, and the reed count will vary from 38^s stock ports to 40^s stock ports depending on the width of the *gamcha*.

The total part of the *Towala gamcha* will consist of mainly two parts, i.e., the selvedge part and the body part. Again, this selvedge part of the *Towala gamcha* consists of several parts with their specific names and denting orders, i.e., ‘*Agari* consists of 10 dents’, followed by ‘*Koni* consists of 6 dents’, ‘*Parh* consists of 20/22/25 dents (based on the width of the *gamcha*)’, ‘*Gondi* consists of 24 dents’, ‘*Churi* consists of 6 dents’, and ‘*Matha pati* consists of 30 dents’. This selvedge portion is made up of Plain weave. The body part consists of two parts i.e., ‘*Toila pati* consists of 30 dents’, followed by the check consists of 4 dents, and this pattern of *Toila pati* and Check will continue for the whole body. Here the *Toila pati* is made up of Huck-a-back weave and the check portion is made up of plain weave. Then again, this pattern will end up with the selvedge portion starting with *Matha pati* after completing 26 numbers of *Toila pati* (which also depends on the width of the *gamcha*). So, the total number of *Toila pati* and *Matha pati* on a single *Towala gamcha* will be 26+2=28.

Earlier it was measured that if the number of 2 floats (2 *Phul*) present on the *Toila pati* section (generated due to Huck-a-back weave) is 18, then the warp yarns present on that single *Toila pati* section will be 30 (which also depends on the width of the *gamcha*). The same number of warp yarns is also present in the *Matha pati* section, but the differentiating part is that it is made up of plain weave only.

Theoretically, *Matha pati* and *Toila pati* will form a square on the *gamcha*, which means if in *Matha pati* and *Toila pati*, 15 dents are present, it means the total number of yarns present in *Matha pati* and *Toila pati* is 15 yarns; so, at the time of weft insertion, the total number of yarns should be 15 yarns. But practically it doesn’t happen. The weavers usually insert the picks according to their eye resemblance. On two sides of the *Towala gamcha*, one pattern is created with the combination of some designed motifs termed ‘*Gol dor*’, ‘*Chain*’ and ‘*Cycle chain*’. In total, this combined pattern is called ‘*Dor*’. The layout of a *towala gamcha* is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Layout of towala gamcha

Technical sheet

- Weaving plan drawing

- Loom used – Frame loom
- Name of the weave – Huck-a-back weave, Plain weave
- No. of heald shafts – 04
- Reed count – 38^s stock port to 40^s stock ports (depending on the width of the *gamcha*)
- Count of warp – 2/40 Ne
- Count of weft – 17 Ne
- Drafting plan - 1 end per 1 heald eye (in both the selvedge portion and the body part)
- Denting plan - 2 ends per 1 dent (in the selvedge portion), 1 end per 1 dent (in the body part)
- EPI – 40
- PPI – 42

13. The Production Cost of the Gamcha

The production cost of Kenjakura's handcrafted *gamcha* varies from one type to another. The cost of manufacturing a single *gamcha* is estimated by comparing the cost of its 18-inch length shown in Table 3.

Table 3: The production cost of different types of *gamcha*

Name of the <i>gamcha</i>	Length of the <i>gamcha</i> (in inches)	The cost of that specific length (Rs.)
<i>Plain check gamcha</i>	18	11
<i>Tom-tom plain check gamcha</i>	18	11
<i>Towala gamcha</i>	18	12
<i>Chera-phara gamcha</i>	18	15
<i>Mukum gamcha</i>	18	18
<i>Harkum gamcha</i>	18	19
<i>Choto phul gamcha</i>	18	12
<i>Boro phul gamcha</i>	18	11
<i>Bibi dial gamcha</i>	18	18
<i>Honeycomb gamcha</i>	18	18

14. The Present Condition of the Craft

This is a conclusive piece based on the observation and interaction with artisans in the Kenjakura village.

- The number of genuine practitioners of traditional handloom weaving is decreasing day by day. Thus, slowly, the handloom sector is coming to an end.
- Government subsidies are not reaching the ground level of artisans properly. Most of them are not aware of any government subsidy.
- The artisans are mostly uneducated, so they fail to produce crafts more effectively or learn about government policies and benefits.
- The cost of raw materials has increased, but the remuneration of weavers and the selling price of woven goods have not increased.
- The younger generation is not allowed to participate because of the current market conditions. They are losing interest in learning or following traditional weaving over time.
- The lifestyle, in general, is very slow-paced, and the work environment is extremely informal.
- Product diversification is limited.
- Due to the increase of mill-made *gamcha* in the market, the demand for handloom *gamcha* is becoming very low.
- The artisans are finding another source of income for their basic needs, which can't be fulfilled by weaving the *gamchas*.

15. Conclusion

Previously, Bankura *gamcha* enjoyed a very good market throughout West Bengal. However, as a result of commercialisation, the competition between mill-made *gamcha* is increasing day by day. The common people were influenced to choose mill-made *gamcha* due to their inability to identify the exact handloom product and their desire to purchase a cheaper one. This issue can be resolved if there is a proper marketing strategy and channel to

sell the products. Artisans sell this *gamcha* alongside other textile items because handloom *gamcha* do not generate as much revenue on the market. Based on the interactions with the artisans and after a detailed survey, the following measures can be taken to improve this traditional craft:

- Measures must be taken to educate the younger generation on traditional *gamcha* weaving techniques.
- It is necessary to generate demand among local residents and make them aware of this traditional craft and its cultural significance and value.
- Provide incentives for artisans to visit government centres for proper training and instruction on how to increase their rate of productivity and profit.
- Craftsmen could be instructed to lead workshops for schools, summer camps, etc. This could assist them in promoting their craft, generating income, and encouraging others to learn and continue the craft traditions.
- Product diversification should go beyond the *gamcha* to reach a broader range of consumers.
- The middleman who purchases woven products from artisans and sells them on the physical market, can open online stores to reach a broader consumer base.
- Conducting a public education campaign to obtain the GI Tag and Handloom Mark for this handwoven *gamcha*.
- According to the current situation, the major threat to the traditional *gamcha* weaving craft is the growing demand for *gamcha* woven on power looms. Ordinary people typically cannot tell the difference between the two, and they are willing to pay less for *gamcha* produced by that mill. If these factors can be managed, then the market demand for Bankura's traditional handwoven *gamcha* will increase significantly.

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